

Self – Confidence and Women Empowerment

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Abstract

A confident woman becomes an empowered woman. Empowered women transmit many tangible and intangible benefits to the family, the community the nation and the entire human race. Self-Confidence makes the educated women as empowered women. A well educated woman becomes an asset to her society, country and the world. Self – Confidence leads the women with leadership qualities. Empowered Women are expressing their opinion and suggestions boldly in public. Social network helps women to have more support and gives greater opportunity to effect change in their society. Empowering women is not that very much easy. It needs more power and strengths. When women feel and work good, they will automatically improve their confidence to empower themselves.

Introduction

Today the empowerment of women has become one of the most important concerns of 21st century. The concept of women empowerment is a recent one. The first year of new millennium 2001 was declared as “Women empowerment year”. Women are the builders and moulders of a nation’s destiny. Women empowerment means emancipating the women from the vicious grips of social, economical, political, caste and gender-based discrimination. It means granting women the freedom to make life choices. Self – Confidence is the stuff of women that turns thoughts into action. We have to maintain the status of women empowerment in India using various aspects like women’s house hold decision power, financial autonomy, freedom of movement, political participation, exposure to media and accesses to education. Generally the women of India are relatively disempowered and they enjoy somewhat lower status than that of men. Women with high levels of confidence have both high – self efficiency and low fear of failures. Self – Confidence that helps women to break the barriers in the society and empower them to eliminate self doubt to achieve their full potential.

Self – Confidence Leads to Women Empowerment

Self – Confidence is a trait that helps women to empower themselves. Self – Confidence is ability to be certain about women’s competencies and skills. It includes a sense of self-esteem and self-assurance. It is one of the best tools that empower the women. Self – Confidence in women will empower them to march ahead to economic prosperity, social justice and equality. It helps the women to achieve social empowerment, educational empowerment, economical and occupational empowerment, legal empowerment and political empowerment. Empowerment of women benefits all. The beneficiaries are not only women alone but also the whole nation. In India in which, our empowered women are realized their full potential – from shaping the future of their families to shaping the future of the nation.

Social Women Empowerment

Empowerment of a woman leads to a better family and ultimately an ideal society to a progressive nation. Social empowerment of women is the promotion of gender equality. Gender equality implies a society in which men and women enjoy the same opportunities, outcomes, rights and obligation in all spheres of life. Empowered women are the key agents for development. They play catalytic towards achievement of social changes required for sustainable development. Social Empowerment of women is essential, not only for the well-being of the individuals but also for overall development of the society. Indian Social Scientists have recognized that all development in the nation is intricately linked with the development of women and their position in this society.

Educational Women Empowerment

Mahatma Gandhi once said; “If you educate a man, you educate an individual, however if you educate a woman, you educate a whole family”. Education is a potent tool to progress in life. It serves as a catalyst and gives women the much deserved platform to set themselves free and rise as equals. The internet and the social media have introduced online women education in a big way. It provides opportunities for e-learning and to open earning avenues for women. Education is considered as a mile stone for women empowerment. It enables them to respond to the challenges to confront their traditional role and change their lives. As education is both an input and output of human development it eliminates gender discrimination. Education has expanded the concept of women empowerment. The female literacy levels according to the Literacy Rate 2011 Census are 65.46 percent. Substantial progress has been achieved in women education since India won its independence. According to the findings of National Sample Survey Office (NSSO), literacy rate among age group of seven years and above in the country was 75 percent. Even beyond literacy, there is much that education can do for women’s rights, dignity and security. Education is the key to unlock the golden door of freedom for development.

Economical Women Empowerment

Opportunity must be created to empower the women to enable them to acquire the skills necessary for entering newly emerging occupations. Women are vital and productive workers in India’s National Economy. Women work for longer hours than men and contribute substantially to family income. Majority of the agriculture workers are women. Towards women’s economic empowerment, Women’s Self – Help and Savings Groups are on the increase and their efficiency is noteworthy. Empowering women is not only for the economic development for their family but also for overall economic productivity of the country. Women are the upholders of the traditions and the progenitors of change and they have the real power of supervising economic activity.

Legal Women Empowerment

The importance of women is recognized by the constitution of India. It not only accorded equality to women but also empowered the state to take steps to uplift the status of women. The constitution provides way to social and economical development of women and their participation in decision making. The importance of women as an important human resource was realized by the framers of the Constitution of India. The constitution of India provides equality to women, in India. A number of Articles of the Constitution focused towards the socio – economic development of women.

- Article 14 Men and women to have equal rights and opportunities in the political, economic and social spheres.
- Article 15(1) Prohibits discrimination against any citizens on the grounds of religion, race, sex, caste, etc.
- Article 16 Equality of opportunities in matter of public appointments for all citizens.
- Article 39 (d) Equal pay for equal work for both men and women.
- Article 42 The state to make provision for ensuring first and humane conditions of work and maternity relief.
- Government has also enacted specific laws to safeguard the interests of women and for upgradation of their status.
- The Hindu succession Act, 1956 which provides for women the right to parental property.
- The Dowry prohibition Act, 1961 which declares the taking of dowry an unlawful activity and thereby prevents the exploitation of women.
- Equal Remuneration Act, 1976 which provides payment of remuneration equal with men for work of equal value.
- The Medical Termination of pregnancy Act, 1971 which legalizes abortion conceding the right of a women to go for abortion on the ground of physical and mental health.
- The Criminal law Amendment Act, 1983 which seeks to stop various types of crimes against women. The Indecent Representation of women (prohibition) Act, 1986 which prohibits the vulgar presentation of women in the media such as newspapers, cinema, T.V. etc.
- The protection of women from Domestic violence Act, 2005 provides for more effective protection of the rights of women guaranteed under the constitution who are victims of violence of any kind occurring within the family.

Legislation has been passed to reserve 33% percent of the seats for women in Panchayatraj and Local Self Government to encourage empowerment of women. It has given an encouragement for women by Government of India to serve parliament and state assemblies. In this regard it is proved how women have given an excellent account of themselves and established themselves in every field. Women have a position of equality in law and initiatives to serve for the welfare of the Nation.

Political Women Empowerment

The most significant changes in empowering women attain their rights to participate in the Indian democracy not just as voters but also as leaders. Our National Leader and former Prime Minister of India Mrs. Indira Gandhi had a vision and dreams for the development of our country. She has built a strong, united and prosperous India with respect and dignity in the world. We have to appreciate and admire the efficiency of our Regional Leaders Selvi Jaya Lalitha former Chief Minister of Tamilnadu, Miss Mayavathi the former Chief Minister of Uttar Pradesh and Miss Mamdha Banarjee Chief Minister of West Bengal for their deep sense of devotion and dedication for the welfare and development of their respective states. They elevated the standard of their states to greater heights.

Contribution of Government and Non-Governmental organizations for Empowerment of Women

A number of governmental policies and programmes have been evolved for the empowerment of women. This enabled them to widen their scope of their contribution to the countries development. Government policies have been formulated to improve the status of women and increased their social awareness. To empower the women in India the Government has taken many initiatives to improve the social status, financial independence and political representation of women. While the government has taken sensitive and responsive steps for women development it is also necessary that academic institutions and non governmental organizations have to be co-ordinated to maximize the results. That is one more category of organizations for achieving rapid economic empowerment of women. And these are Women's Cooperative Societies and Self-Help Groups. These organizations are placed to promote women empowerment.

Conclusion

We need to strengthen the formal system and simultaneously develop alternative system of women empowerment effective in a large scale. We need to overhaul the management of women empowerment. We need to mobilize local communities for the cause of women empowerment. We need to improve self-confidence, motivation and performance. Thus the marathon race is ahead of us before we reach the goals of women empowerment. In this task, however we have an important new ally namely the self-confidence. The key to development and the key to progress is women empowerment. Without women empowerment that there can be no development or progress. What we are all doing for the empowerment of women today will shape India's tomorrow.

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